

Towards Multi-viewpoint Ontology Construction by Collaboration of Non-experts and Crowdsourcing: The Case of the Effect of Diet on Health¹

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Abstract

Domain experts are skilled to build a narrow ontology that reflects their sub-field of expertise, based on their work experience and personal beliefs. We call this type of ontology a single-viewpoint ontology. There can be a variety of such single viewpoint ontologies that represent a wide spectrum of sub-fields and expert opinions on the domain. But to have a complete formal vocabulary for the domain they need to be linked and unified into a multi-viewpoint model, while having the subjective viewpoint statements marked and distinguished from the objectively true statements. In this study we propose and implement a two-phase methodology for multi-viewpoint ontology construction by non-expert users. The proposed methodology was implemented for the domain of the effect of diet on health. A large-scale crowdsourcing experiment was conducted with about 750 ontological statements that aimed to determine whether each of these statement is objectively true, viewpoint or erroneous. Typically, in crowdsourcing experiments the workers are asked for their personal opinions on the given subject. However, in our case their ability to objectively assess others' opinions was examined as well. Our results show substantially higher accuracy in classification for the objective assessment approach compared to the experiment based on personal opinions.

Introduction

Ontology construction task involves extensive human expert participation/effort. The experts are able to build ontologies of high professional quality, but they are hard to find and expensive to employ. In a recent review Simperl and Luczak-Rösch (2014) assert that today it is generally acknowledged that ontologies should be developed and

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maintained in a community-driven manner, with tools providing collaboration platforms, enabling ontology stakeholders to exchange ideas and discuss modelling decisions. Muresan and Klavans (2013) argue that specialized medical terminologies, such as SNOMED CT (<http://www.ihtsdo.org/snomed-ct/>) cannot provide sufficient support when integrated into consumer-oriented applications because they do not include lay vocabulary required for these applications. Hence, numerous methodologies were proposed for collaborative ontology construction by non-expert users (Pereira, 2008; Kalbasi, Janowicz, Reitsma, Boerboom, and Alesheikh, 2014; Simperl and Luczak-Rösch, 2014). With the advent of the social tagging, folksonomies (user-generated taxonomies) have been constructed based on user tags as “wisdom of the crowds” (Kotis & Papasalouros, 2011; Lin & Chen, 2012). Recently several works have effectively utilized micro-task crowdsourcing technique for ontology construction, error detection and verification (Noy, Mortensen, Alexander and Musen; Mortensen, Musen, and Noy, 2013; Mortensen et al., 2015).

In addition to high price and low availability, experts tend to build narrow *single-viewpoint* ontologies which capture their individual opinions, beliefs and work experience, but which might be unacceptable for other experts. As discussed in (Hjørland, 2015) relations in thesauri and other terminologies are not context-free, definitional, and true in all possible worlds. This is especially true for controversial domains with a diversity of (contradictory) viewpoints and no single ground truth. More comprehensive modeling of such controversies requires a new type of ontology that allows for multiple (contradictory) viewpoints of the domain to co-exist as proposed in (Zhitomirsky-Geffet and Erez, 2014; Zhitomirsky-Geffet and Bar-Ilan, 2014; Doerr, Kritsotaki & Boutsika, 2011). The optimal way to create a multi-viewpoint ontology would be to gather a large number of domain experts with different opinions, such that they together cover all the variety of opinions that exist on the domain. However, in practice, in many cases locating and gathering such a diverse and representative group of domain experts and having them do the tagging (for hundreds of statements) is impossible and unaffordable. Thus, for such cases, we propose an alternative way to create an ontology based on the professional literature available on the web which naturally presents a variety of experts’ opinions on the domain. In this setting, we anticipate that non-expert subjects and particularly information specialists specifically guided can be effectively employed who are also easier to be recruited.

Our aim in this research is to propose and implement a methodology for multi-viewpoint ontology construction by non-experts in the specified domain of knowledge. The general methodology comprises two steps: 1) collaborative construction of an ontology with diverse viewpoints on the domain; 2) classification and annotation of the obtained ontological statements into three categories: absolute truth, controversial viewpoint and error. To ensure the quality of the ontology constructed by non-expert users the key-idea behind the first step is that all the

ontological entities and statements are extracted from authorized professional scientific literature.

To implement the proposed approach a user study was performed. Then, to classify the obtained ontological statements, a series of large-scale crowdsourcing experiments were conducted. In particular, we explore the crowdsourcing workers' perception of consensus and subjectivity of the presented statements. To this end, two alternative approaches to design of crowdsourcing experiments were tested: 1) Personal opinion of the workers on the given subject, e.g. "I agree that this statement is true"; 2) Objective assessment of others' opinions on the given subject, e.g. "Everybody agrees that this statement is true"; "Some of the experts agree with this statement while some others disagree".

Then, a number of aggregation measures were employed and compared to derive the collective decision out of the crowds' votes. The main research questions quantitatively assessed in this study are as follows:

- 1) Whether statement classification gains higher accuracy when crowdsourcing workers express their own subjective opinions or when they try to objectively assess what others would think of the given statement?
- 2) How different aggregation measures influence the obtained results?

We found that consistently better results were obtained when workers had to objectively assess others' opinions than when asked to express their own opinions. The accuracy of classification by crowdsourcing was quite high when applying machine learning aggregation methods and much lower for the other methods.

The significance of modeling multi-viewpoint ontologies emerges from users need to see a systemized wide spectrum of opinions on their topic of interest (An, Quercia, & Crowcroft, 2013). This diversity cannot be expected to be achieved when domain experts (e.g. physicians, nutritionists or other individual specialists) construct the ontology due to natural leaning in favor of their personal opinions. Hence, thoroughly designed crowdsourcing combined with computational techniques can be key for providing users with a desired diversity of professional information. In order to enable data integration and interoperability, statements (representing facts and opinions) from diverse sources are to be unified into a multi-viewpoint ontological model. Multi-viewpoint information tagging (Ouzrout, Geryville, Bouras, and Sapidis, 2009) and retrieval (Geryville, 2007), document summarization (Paul, Zhai, and Girju, 2010), and sentiment and opinion mining (Liu and Gruen, 2012) frameworks will benefit from a multi-viewpoint ontology.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. The next section provides definitions and technical background for understanding concepts and methods used in the paper. Then related literature is reviewed. Further, we present our methods, then the results of our experiments are presented and discussed in the Results and discussion section

and the Final remarks section sets out some conclusions and directions for future work.

Background

Ontologies provide a formal common terminology for humans and automatic agents on the given domain of knowledge (Gruber, 1993; Noy & McGuinness, 2000). They are employed in many fields of science from humanities (the CIDOC-CRM ontology: <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/>) to medicine (the Gene ontology (<http://amigo.geneontology.org/amigo>)).

In the standard ontological model which represents only consensual knowledge of the domain every statement (RDF-style triple: $\langle concept1 \text{ relationship } concept2 \rangle$) can be annotated as true or false. Recently, Aroyo and Welty (2013) suggested that disagreement in crowd votes in crowdsourcing-based classification indicates vagueness or ambiguity in a sentence or in the relations being extracted. Crowdsourcing is based on a group of anonymous non-experts who independently fulfill a series of simple tasks. Their results are further aggregated into a collective opinion, which is shown to be as good as the domain expert's answers and for a much lower price (Howe, 2006; Quinn & Bederson, 2011; Cooper et al., 2010).

In the context of multiple viewpoint ontologies we assume that disagreement reflects a viewpoint statement for which contradictory opinions exist. Therefore, statements (triples) in a multi-viewpoint ontology are classified into three categories (truth values): absolute truth, subjective viewpoint and error. We define as “absolute truth” consensual statements for which there is a case/world/situation when only a single positive and widely agreed opinion exists; for “viewpoint” statements for all cases there are multiple opinions, some of which agree with the truth of the statement and the others disagree; “errors” are statements with logical or ontological flaws.

As a case study we chose the domain of diet: how food affects health. Numerous thesauri, classifications and vocabularies exist for the biomedical and healthcare domain, such as the Gene ontology (<http://amigo.geneontology.org/amigo>), the International classification of diseases (ICD), the USDA Food and Human Nutrition thesaurus for hierarchy of foods and nutrients, large drug vocabularies (e.g. RxNorm, National drug file), and SNOMED CT (Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine Clinical Terms), a broad terminology for healthcare. Most of them consist of taxonomic relations, such as (*pneumonia IS-A lung disease*), while SNOMED CT includes also non-taxonomic relationships between different categories, such as (*common cold causative agent virus*).

However, no ontology exists, to the best of our knowledge, for inter-relations and influence of food on body functioning and diseases. This domain is a very intensely explored field of science. There are important questions such as: what product lowers hypertension? or whether soy can prevent cancer? New findings and recommendations are published every year that sometimes contradict previous research results. Thus, a healthy diet is a highly controversial topic. Therefore, a comprehensive ontology for this domain has to capture heterogeneity in domain experts' opinions. As a basis, the concepts and taxonomic relations might be adopted

to construct the hierarchy of classes from the existing ontologies mentioned above, so that non-experts do not have to define the class structure themselves. Another reason for choosing the “nutrition effect on health” domain is that it might be considered a borderline between scientific and pseudo-scientific information which allows a wide variety of opinions. To provide as accurate information as possible non-experts are guided to extract ontological statements solely from authorized scientific literature.

A practical contribution of this study is the multi-viewpoint ontology for diet which is an important supplement to the set of ontologies in the biomedical domain. Based on our ontology an intelligent decision making service that draws an objective picture of pros and cons for different foods can be developed showing diverse health problems and benefits caused (directly and indirectly) by various food products. The resulting multi-viewpoint ontology was published on the website: <http://www.edenerez.com/crowdiet>.

Literature Review

We first review related work in the area of ontology construction and particularly collaborative ontology construction by non-experts. Further, we describe studies that apply and assess the effectiveness of crowdsourcing for ontology engineering.

Collaborative ontology construction

One of the earliest works on cooperative ontology construction was presented by (Maedche and Staab, 2001), which facilitates a graphical user interface for manual ontology creation enhanced by ontology refining and automatic extraction of ontological entities based on natural language processing algorithms. In the past years, several frameworks were proposed for collaborative ontology construction and integration (Pereira, 2008; Shvaiko and Euzenat, 2013; Euzenat and Shvaiko, 2013; Simperl and Luczak-Rösch, 2014). The most crucial phase in the collaborative process is reaching agreements on the resulting ontology. Three possible approaches to do this exist: 1) by intersection - where only the shared part of the different users' ontologies is included in the resulting ontology; 2) by union - where all the components constructed by different users are included in the final ontology; 3) by revision - where users might independently revise others' ontological components to reach a consensual ontology version. The intersection approach was adopted by numerous works. For example, the PROMPT system (Noy and Musen, 2003) looks for similar concepts (classes) in the ontologies and displays possible conflicts and finds possible solutions to these conflicts. In the Collaborative Protégé environment (Tudorache et al., 2008) it is possible to reach an agreement by user voting or by a direct chat/discussion between the users. In several studies (Heflin, 2001; Holsapple and Joshi, 2002; Gómez-Gauchía et al., 2004; Karapiperis and Apostolou, 2006) the participants went through an iterative process of disagreement discussion until all the controversial viewpoints were eliminated. In these studies the Delphi method for collecting views of several subjects and the Nominal Group Technique (GNT) technique to make collective decisions in groups that meet face-to-face were employed. Kalbasi, Janowicz, Reitsma, Boerboom and Alesheikh (2014) presented a

methodology for collaborative ontology construction in two steps with a minimal initial ontology to start with in Geosciences. The participants were ontology engineers, who were not experts in the domain of knowledge and domain experts, who had no background in ontology engineering and knowledge organization. According to their approach only components with full consensus were inserted into the resulting ontology.

The union approach is represented by (Vrandecic, Vr, Pinto, Sure and Tempich, 2005) introduce a DILIGENT methodology which allows for co-existence of multiple local ontologies created by end-users on the basis of the given core ontology. All the decisions on the shared (merged) version of the ontology are made by a board of domain experts. Another prominent example of the union approach is the HCOME methodology and tool (Kotis and Vouros, 2006). As opposed to DILIGENT, this methodology provides the users, knowledge workers, with tools for discussion of the shared version of the ontology, argumentation, problem resolution and modification.

The revision approach was applied in CRAFT (Liu and Gruen, 2008) where three ontologies for a specific domain were developed dynamically by nine trained subjects. In their experiments there was no direct interaction between the subjects. The consensus was achieved by switching ontologies three times during the course of the experiment and continuing to construct the ontology started by others.

Thus, as can be noticed, most of the above frameworks force the users to reach a consensus on their final ontology. In contrast, our approach is to intentionally guide the users to construct multiple viewpoint ontologies and then integrate them together, where multiple viewpoints are part of the central unified ontology and are annotated as such. Another novelty of our approach is that we merge personal ontologies by locating matching, contradictory or unrelated (complementary) statements rather than by finding matching concepts as done in the above systems. An initial study in this direction was performed by (Zhitomirsky-Geffet and Erez, 2014). The authors/researchers asked a group of about 20 information science students to independently construct and then collaboratively annotate the statements in a multi-viewpoint ontology in the controversial field of "Jewish tradition and society". In this study, we partially adopt their methodology for initial personal ontologies' creation.

Micro-task crowdsourcing for ontology engineering

In this subsection we review studies that apply and assess the effectiveness of crowdsourcing for scientific tasks and particularly for ontology engineering.

Crowdsourcing is employed to take a job traditionally performed by domain experts and outsource it to an undefined large group of people typically for a small reward or payment (Howe, 2006; Quinn and Bederson, 2011). This practice has been proven effective in promoting scientific projects (Cooper et al., 2010) especially in cases of very large jobs, lack of domain experts and limited budget. The underlying

technology behind micro-task crowdsourcing is recruiting a group of anonymous non-expert workers through some crowdsourcing site/s, such as Amazon Mechanical Turk or CrowdFlower for a given simple task. Each worker is assigned a series of tasks, e.g. questions with a number of possible answers and is asked to select the most correct one in his opinion. To improve the quality of the replies, the workers on the site can be preliminary tested on a small sample of qualification questions and only those who passed the test are selected for the real/main experiment. The workers' replies are further aggregated into a collective decision.

Recently, numerous studies have been conducted to evaluate the quality of the crowdsourcing technology for ontology engineering. An initial attempt in this direction was recently performed by (Sarasua, Simperl and Noy, 2012) who asked the participants on Mechanical Turk to decide whether a pair of concepts (classes) in ontologies constitutes a match or not. In (Noy, Mortensen, Alexander and Musen, 2013; Mortensen et al., 2013) the authors present their studies on verification of the ontology's taxonomic relations (is-a-kind-of, IS-A) by micro-task crowdsourcing. They asked the participants at the Amazon Mechanical Turk crowdsourcing platform to answer simple true/false questions formulated for the taxonomic relations from a few existing ontologies in the biomedical domain, such as "*Is Heart always an Organ*". Their goal was to compare the relations judged as true by the turkers to the "ground truth" relations from the ontology constructed by domain experts. The researchers reported quite high levels of average precision (88%) compared to the ground truth ontology. In (Mortensen et al., 2015) similar methodology was employed to detect critical errors in a large biomedical terminology(SNOMED). Bayesian inference was utilized to aggregate the workers results. The results of the crowds were as good as the domain experts' ones. They conclude that professional tasks can be effectively performed by crowds.

In this study, we continue the above line of work. We further develop it to apply crowdsourcing for classification of statements in multi-viewpoint ontology. While several works have presented a methodology for collaborative construction of consensual ontologies (e.g., Tudorache, Noy, Tu and Musen, 2008; Noy and Musen, 2003), to the best of our knowledge this work is the first one to propose an end-to-end methodology for collaborative construction of multi-viewpoint ontologies.

The main methodological differences between our approach and the previous work are as follows. As opposed to previous studies in our experiments the tasks presented to the workers were not binary (true/false) votes, but rather a multi-class classification of the ontological statements with 3-5 optional categories to choose from. Another new aspect is that the statements were not only with is-a-kind-of (IS-A) relationship, but also included a variety of domain-specific relationships, such as, *cures*, *causes*, *increases-the-risk-of*. Hence, our tasks are more cognitively complicated for the workers. Instead of comparing workers collective decisions to the domain experts' answers which are suspected to be leaned/skewed, we build a gold standard annotation according to the scientific literature. To aggregate the workers results state-of-the-art multi-class machine classification algorithms were employed. In the

next section we present a detailed description of our method.

Methods

In this section we provide a detailed specification of the proposed two-step methodology for collaborative construction of ontology by non-experts and classification of its statements by crowdsourcing. We also describe the aggregation methods for crowdsourcing output that were employed in this study.

A methodology for collaborative construction of ontology with diverse viewpoints on the domain by non-experts

1. Viewpoints (sub-topics) selection

As a first step, the main controversial sub-topics and concepts of the domain of knowledge are to be determined. This can be done by looking up the scientific literature for articles explicitly stating controversial sub-topics in the research of the domain. In addition, advice may be sought from domain experts.

2. Individual ontology construction per viewpoint based on the scientific literature

Next, a group of subjects who are information professionals is to be divided into sub-groups and each sub-group is assigned a certain sub-topic of the domain. At the first step, every subject in the group has to work alone. Defining and delimiting the essential characteristics of a class cannot be done by non-experts. Therefore, to ensure the high professional quality of the ontology despite the fact that it is constructed by non-experts in the domain, the participants should be instructed to search for scientific literature on their sub-topic where only professional websites such as standard thesauri, government and academic sites (with .gov and .edu suffices) and peer-reviewed refereed scientific journals and conference proceedings are considered as reliable sources for this purpose. Domain experts might be consulted in order to extract a list of such reliable sources for the given domain. Wikipedia, blogs, social networks and other pseudo-scientific and non-academic sites as well as personal opinions of the participants are not allowed to be used. The subjects have to extract only ontological triples that support the viewpoint on the domain they were assigned to.

3. Single-viewpoint ontology creation

Next, like in the previous studies (Karaparis, 2012; Kalbasi et al., 2014) the subjects who have worked on the same viewpoint ontology have to reach consensus and construct one consistent unified viewpoint ontology. To this end, all the statements from the individual ontologies are pooled together and their unified vocabulary has to be normalized by the subjects according to the following guidelines: (i) typos, morphological differences, different spellings of a word are to be brought to a standard form; (ii) synonyms are to be unified (e.g. "*body part*" – "*body region*"); (iii) "orphans" - terms without super-class – are to be linked to their super-classes; (iv)

redundancies are to be removed, e.g. given the statements from different single-viewpoint ontologies: vitamin B12 *IS-A* vitamin B, vitamin B12 *IS-A* vitamin, vitamin B *IS-A* vitamin, then the second statement is redundant and should be removed; (v) *IS-A* statements for concepts that were never used in a non-taxonomic relation throughout the ontology should be eliminated as well. Note that the steps (iii), (iv) and (v) can be done automatically, while the other steps can be implemented semi-automatically with assistance of existing natural language processing tools for ontology alignment (Shvaiko and Euzenat, 2013) and existing standard domain thesauri.

4. Unified multi-viewpoint ontology creation

Finally, these viewpoint ontologies constructed by different groups of subjects are unified into one multi-viewpoint ontology, which might include contradictory statements representing distinct viewpoints in the professional literature. To this end, for the unified ontology the above normalization steps should be repeated by representatives from every subgroup of subjects.

A methodology for ontological statements classification by crowdsourcing

1. Designing the crowdsourcing experiment

Once the ontology has been constructed as described above, its statements are to be classified to distinguish between true, viewpoint and erroneous statements by a group of subjects. As opposed to the previous study (Zhitomirsky-Geffet and Erez, 2014) in this research we propose to assess the quality of employing micro-task crowdsourcing for this goal. To this end, at first, a questionnaire should be devised for crowdsourcing workers. The number of questions – *micro-tasks* – can be determined by the number of statements to classify. The general scheme for each question is as follows: What is the most correct assertion for the given statement: <statement>, <assertion1> <assertion2> ...<assertionN>. The assertions correspond to the three above-mentioned categories (true, viewpoint, error) but can be formulated in different ways. This allows to study the influence of the assertion type on the workers' classification accuracy. In order to filter out automatic robots, cheaters and unqualified workers, a set of representative questions for the qualification test is composed and given to the workers prior to the main experiment. The number of workers for each micro-task and the minimal number of questions each worker has to complete before he is allowed to quit the experiment are predetermined.

2. Gold standard generation

To evaluate the accuracy of the obtained classification a golden standard annotation of the dataset is required. This is especially challenging if there is no existing experimental benchmark or gold standard for topic, and thus there is no way to compare the obtained ontology to a similar professional domain ontology. An individual domain expert's (a physician, a nutritionist or another health care professional in our case) answers are suspected to be biased in favor of his/her personal opinions. In an ideal situation the optimal way to create a golden standard

would be if we could gather a large number of domain experts with different opinions on the topic, such that they together cover all the variety of opinions that exist on the domain. Then ontological statements tagged differently by different domain experts would be classified as viewpoints, while statement with full agreement among the experts would be tagged as absolute truth. This approach of scientific curation of ontologies based on domain expert peer review was proposed by (Smith et al., 2007; Smith, 2008). However, the authors admitted that there was still a need for creating incentives to motivate domain experts to invest time and effort into this task. Therefore, in practice, in many cases locating and gathering such a diverse and representative group of domain experts and having them do the tagging (for hundreds of statements) is impossible and unaffordable. Thus, for such cases, when there is no practical way to recruit a large group of domain experts with a wide variety of opinions, we propose an alternative way to create a gold standard based on the available on the web professional literature which naturally presents a variety of experts' opinions on the domain.

Therefore, we build a gold standard annotation according to the scientific literature. To this end, a panel of information professionals (who have not participated in the ontology creation experiment) classify as "true" only statements for which no professional/academic source was located that contradicted them, as "viewpoint" they classify statements for which there was at least one reliable source that contradicted them and another reliable source that supported them, as "error" they classify statements comprising ontological/logical errors (e.g. wrong or inversed semantic relationship). In cases of disagreement between the panel members they reach a consensus through a direct discussion. The panel should consist of information search specialists with a wide experience in seeking medical information for enterprises and large organizations, for which it is crucial to not to miss any existing information. Thus, if none of these professional information seekers located contradictory information for the statement, then this result is reliable and this statement can be considered as absolute truth. This might not be as optimal as the ideal case of domain expert-diversity-based annotation described above, but still is quite accurate and more practical to accomplish.

Next, we need to provide a formal definition for our three-category annotation model. One possible approach for dealing with more than two truth values in ontologies has been presented in (Ding & Peng, 2004). The authors developed BayesOWL, a framework which augments and supplements the semantic web ontology language OWL for representing and reasoning with uncertainty based on Bayesian networks (BN). BayesOWL defines a set of rules and procedures for direct translation of an OWL ontology into a BN directed acyclic graph (DAG). Each class can be represented as a variable and two types of probability can be assigned to it: the prior probability (PriorProb class) and the conditional probability (CondProb class). However, this methodology cannot be adopted in our study since we assign various truth values to statements (triples) with different types of predicates rather than to individual classes.

It has been shown that fuzzy logic allows one to bridge the gap between human-

understandable soft logic and machine-readable hard logic. Fuzzy ontologies have been defined as a theoretical paradigm incorporating fuzzy logic (Calegary & Sanchez, 2008). The authors further define a new fuzzy relationship called *semantic correlation* which links between concepts in a fuzzy ontology. Another instrument for statements annotation for uncertainty has been recently proposed by (Bobillo & Straccia, 2011). To this end, they employ fuzzy logic to extend the OWL2 language. They define an optional tag *Degree*, with an attribute *value*, which is applied to encode the degree of truth for a given assertion. In our case, it is hard to estimate and quantify the degree of uncertainty or fuzziness of a statement. This is since it is hard to assess how many domain experts in the world and what proportion of all the existing scientific literature on the domain support or oppose a given ontological statement. Therefore, we propose to use a “viewpoint” as a third truth value (in addition to true and false/error) as follows.

For formal annotation by three categories of truth values, a CRM_{inf} ontology (Stead et al. 2015), an extension of the CIDOC-CRM model, can be adopted. In CRM_{inf} every statement (proposition) can be represented as an instance of *I6_Belief* class which can be assigned a truth value. The model allows for using more than two truth values, as needed in our case where three truth values are employed. The annotated ontological statements (beliefs) can be further used for logical inference, reasoning and argumentation.

3. Methods for result aggregation and evaluation

After running the crowdsourcing experiment an aggregation measure has to be devised and applied to determine the final crowds' decision on classification for each statement.

In this study we propose the following baseline measures:

1. As a first baseline for our classification task we calculate the accuracy (compared to the gold standard annotation) for a plain "all true annotation" strategy. In other words, since our test set is unbalanced and most of the statements are true, a worker decides to annotate all the statements as true.
2. The second baseline measure is computed as the proportion of correct judgments (based on the gold standard) out of all the individual judgments made by the workers during the course of the experiment.

Then, the following aggregation methods are applied to capture the "wisdom of crowds" classification and further compared to the above baselines:

1. The first aggregation technique applies only to statements on which the majority of workers (over 50% and over 75%) agreed in voting. The accuracy of the workers' majority vote is computed according to the gold standard.
2. The second metric considers the accuracy of the most popular vote among the workers for a statement (even if it was not a majority vote as above).

3. As a state-of-the-art baseline we compute the measure employed for crowdsourcing aggregation by (Mortensen et al., 2013), which is based on Bayesian inference with beta distribution (with $\alpha=0.5$ and $\beta=0.5$ for Jeffrey's prior).
4. Finally, we employ state-of-the-art supervised machine learning algorithms: SVM (support vector machine) and MLP (multi layered perceptron) to classify the statements using the workers' votes as features. Every assertion in the form (that workers can choose as answer) represents a single feature. The amount of user votes for this assertion is the feature's weight for the statement.

To evaluate the performance of the classification results we use the following state-of-the-art methods: Accuracy in ten-fold cross validation, ROC AUC (area under the ROC curve) which measures the probability that the correct class is ranked higher than any other label, and Kappa (Cohen, 1960) coefficient, that computes the observed agreement between two classifications relatively to the chance agreement.

We also used Informedness proposed by (Powers, 2007), as the probability of an informed decision, to overcome the bias problem with accuracy: as argued in (Powers, 2007) accuracy is biased when the dataset is unbalanced and thus does not reflect a real improvement over chance classification.

Experimental setup

To implement the proposed methodology, we conducted a user study with 16 participants who were all graduate students at the Department of Information Science at Bar-Ilan University. In the realm of diet three basic product types – milk, meat (including poultry) and soy were chosen as most disputable based on advice of three senior clinical diet experts. Based on these products four diet approaches were defined each reflecting a different viewpoint on their effect on human health. "Chinese" (shows the negative impact of milk and its products and supports soy products), "Vegetarian" (argues the negative impact of meat and its products and supports soy as supplement), "Western-pro-meat" (shows the advantages of meat product for human health and disadvantages of soy), "Western-pro-milk" (presents the benefits of dairy products and negative effect of soy). In our experiment these students produced collaboratively four consistent single-viewpoint ontologies for the four distinct diet approaches described above. The upper level concepts provided to the students as a basis for their ontologies included food product, meat product, dairy product, soy product, disease, body organ, nutritional element, physiological system, physiological system functioning. Basic semantic relationships supplied to the students were: IS-A (type-of), part-of, includes, instance-of, causes, cures, treats, hurts, prevents, improves, increases, decreases, affects.

The students were instructed to add more concepts, relationships and statements of the form: *concept1* – *relationship* - *concept2* from the professional literature. According to the domain experts' recommendation, reliable sources in our case were scientific articles with experimental results published and accessible on PubMed, government websites, universities' and public hospitals' portals, for taxonomic relations they

consulted Medical Subject Headings (MeSH: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/mesh/>), International Classification of Diseases (ICD: <http://apps.who.int/classifications/icd10/browse/2010/en>) and US Department of Agriculture (USDA) food and nutrition vocabulary: <http://ndb.nal.usda.gov/ndb/foods#>). Triples extracted solely from scientific papers which describe results of experiments with the above chosen products and their components and which have found effect of these products on human health, particularly various body system functioning and diseases were acceptable. A link to the source article supporting every statement had to be provided. They were instructed to include in their ontologies only the terms and triples related directly to the given sub-topic (e.g. a concept "cereal" could not be included in the "vegetarian diet" since the focus of the sub-topic was meat and soy product only). Each group merged the members' ontologies into one viewpoint ontology for a given type of diet. Every ontology consisted of a set of about 300 RDF-style statements. Each statement conveys a fact on the domain retrieved from a scientific article. Then, these ontologies' vocabularies were standardized and the ontologies were unified into a single multi-viewpoint ontology, which, particularly, included contradictory statements representing distinct viewpoints on the domain. After duplicate elimination there were 776 distinct statements in this ontology. Two information science specialists annotated each of these statements as true, viewpoint or erroneous based on evidence from the scientific literature according to the methodology described in the previous section. As a result, 564 of the statements were annotated as true, 178 as viewpoint and 34 as erroneous. Table 1 presents a sample of the statements of each type.

At the next stage of the study we designed and executed three experiments with workers on the popular CrowdsFlower site.

We define the objective vs. subjective formulation of assertions. The objective assertions express the opinions of other people or domain experts, while the subjective assertions convey the personal beliefs of the individual user. The first experiment contained three possible assertions of the first type (objective evaluation) for every given statement, each directly corresponding to the multi-viewpoint ontological classification scheme: true, erroneous and viewpoint (as presented in Figure 1).

Table 1: A sample of true, viewpoint and erroneous statements from the unified multi-viewpoint ontology according to the gold standard annotation. As can be noticed the erroneous statements can be of different types. Thus, calcium and vitamin D can improve bone density but not each other. Blood is kind of a body fluid but is not a body organ according to the professional thesauri. The fourth erroneous statement has the problem of reversed relationship (as it should have been: "vitamin B12 can be increased by meat product"). The other incorrect statements are characterized by a poor choice of the relationships, such as dairy product is essential *for decrease* of hypertension (but a phrase "for decrease" was missing in the relationship's formulation).

Concept1	Relationship	Concept2
True statements		
meat product	contains	vitamin B12
vitamin B12	reduces-damage-to	nervous system
iron	prevents	anemia
iron	increased-by	red meat
iron	is-a-kind-of	mineral
Viewpoint statements		
dairy product	increases	weight loss
hypertension	increased-by	meat product
isoflavone	decreases-the-risk-of	ovarian cancer
iron	decreases-the-risk-of	hair loss
colon cancer	increased-by	meat product
Errors		
calcium	improved-by	vitamin D
nervous system	increased-by	mineral
blood	is-a-kind-of	body organ
meat product	can-be-increased-by	vitamin B12
dairy product	essential-for	hypertension

Instructions ▾ Experiment 1

Choose your answer for the following statements. Every statement consists of concept1 relationship concept2

for instance: "milk is-a-kind-of dairy product " where "milk" is concept1, "is-a-kind-of" is a relationship and "dairy product" is concept2

The given statement:

calcium *contains* milk

Choose the most correct answer for the given statement:

- Absolutely true: Everyone would agree with this statement
- Wrong statement: Nobody would agree with this statement
- Controversial statement: Some people might agree with this statement but some others might disagree

Figure 1: The form displayed to the workers on CrowdFlower for the first experiment.

The second experiment (see Figure 2) included 5 alternative objective assertions for every statement. As opposed to the former experiment, in this experiment the workers had to assess the expert opinion on the statement with a more fine-grained resolution which included quantitative and temporal quantifiers ("all" vs. "exists", "always" vs. "sometimes") for the amount of cases in which the statement is true, in addition to the amount of experts who agree/disagree with it. Such formulation allows for considering statements that are true only in some cases (according to the definition presented in the Introduction), and is supposed to make the decision clearer for a worker. Thus, assertions 1 and 2 correspond to the true statements, 3 and 4 characterize viewpoint statements (for which there is no case where all experts agree with the statement), and assertion 5 identifies wrong statements.

Instructions ▾ Experiment 2

Choose the most correct answer for the following statements. Every statement consists of concept1 relationship concept2. For example, heart is-a body organ, where heart is concept1, is-a is relationship, and body organ is concept2.

The possible answers are:

1. Absolutely true statement: all the experts agree that this statement is always correct.
2. Sometimes true statement: all the experts agree that this statement is correct in some cases.
3. Partially consensual statement: some experts always agree with this statement while some others disagree with it in some cases.
4. Controversial statement: some experts agree with this statement in some cases, while the others totally disagree with it.
5. Wrong statement: all the experts always disagree with this statement

Figure 2: The form displayed to the workers on CrowdFlower for the second experiment.

Instructions Experiment 3

Choose the most correct answer for the following statements. Every statement consists of concept1 relationship concept2. For example, heart is-a body organ, where heart is concept1, is-a is relationship, and body organ is concept2.

The possible answers are:

1. I agree with this statement since it is always true.
2. I agree that this statement is true in most cases.
3. I agree that this statement is not true in most cases.
4. I disagree with this statement since I agree with a statement that contradicts it.
5. I disagree with this statement since it is logically or semantically incorrect.

Figure 3: The form displayed to the workers on CrowdFlower for the third experiment.

We also experimented with personal assertions. In this case (see Figure 3), we consider statements that this particular subject judges as true (in all or most cases) as true statements (statements 1 and 2) and disagreement due to an ontological error in the statement is considered as “error” (statement 5), while for ontologically correct statements partial agreement or agreement with the contradictory statements is considered as “viewpoint” (statements 3 and 4).

Note that in our preliminary experiments we have also used forms with only two assertions: "I agree with the statement" vs. "I disagree with this statement"; and a form with three assertions: "I agree" vs. "disagree" vs. "partially agree with this statement". But they both yielded lower accuracy results than the form with five assertions presented in Figure 3.

The objective of these crowdsourcing experiments was to test which type of questions and assertions is more effective for ontological statements classification. In particular, it is probably easier for the workers to express their own opinions but the question is whether it also yields more accurate classification results. To this end, we compare the results of experiment 2 (considering experts' opinions) to those of experiment 3 (personal workers' opinions) – both with 5 optional answers.

Another question is whether using quantifiers and more detailed answers contributes to the accuracy of classification? To answer this question we compare the results of experiment 2 (experts' opinions with 5 possible answers) to those of experiment 1 (others' opinions with 3 variants of answers). Our experimental framework differs from Mortensen et al., 2013; Noy et al., 2013; Sarasua et al., 2012) in several aspects: 1) we used 3-5 assertions and 3-class classification of statements as opposed to binary classification and assertion type (true vs. false) in the previous research; 2) various types of ontological relations were classified rather than only IS-A relations as in previous work; 3) we asked users to assess others' opinions and not only their personal opinions.

After an experiment was published as a job on the CrowdFlower site, workers could register in order to take part in it. Forty statements were excluded from the test set and

were used as part of the qualification test to select 40 qualified workers out of all the registered workers for the job. The qualification test included 20 true statements and 20 error statements (10 of the error statements were invented by us - they did not appear in the ontology). Only workers who correctly answered at least 80% of the questions in the qualification test were allowed to participate in the main experiment. The rest 746 statements (544 true statements, 178 viewpoints, 24 errors) were randomly divided into tasks of 40 questions each (the last task only included 26 questions). Eight US cents were paid to a worker for each task. Once every task was executed by 40 different workers the experiment was completed. It took about 12 hours and 64\$ for each of the experiments to be completed.

The measures described in the previous section were applied to aggregate the individual user votes to the "wisdom of crowds" decision. For each measure and experiment (where applicable) we evaluated the performance for two types of classification: 1) 3-class classification that classifies each statement as true, viewpoint or erroneous; and 2) 2-class classification that distinguishes between the true statements and all the others (i.e. viewpoint and erroneous statements were considered as one category). This case was considered in order to compare the obtained results to those in the previous work (Mortensen et al., 2013).

Results and discussion

As shown in Table 2 the MLP and SVM machine learning algorithms elicited the best results (over 90% accuracy). They significantly outperformed all the other aggregation methods by all the performance evaluation measures for all the experiments and classification tasks. For the 1st experiment the Bayesian inference measure produced similar results to the 2-class SVM. We used the Weka system (Hall et al., 2009) implementation for both algorithms with default coefficients' value set. The system implements John Platt's sequential minimal optimization algorithm (Platt, 1998) for training a support vector classifier with PolyKernel, epsilon of 1.0E-12, one seed, the complexity constant of 1 and tolerance value of 0.001. This implementation globally replaces all missing values and transforms nominal attributes into binary ones. It also normalizes all attributes by default. For MLP the default value for the learning rate was set to 0.3, momentum value was 0.2 and training time was 500 iterations.

Aggregation method	Experiment 1	Experiment 2	Experiment 3
Accuracy-based evaluation			
"All true" baseline	0.73	0.73	0.73
Individual worker judgments baseline 2-class	0.71	0.76	0.73
Individual worker judgments baseline 3-class	0.76	0.79	0.76
Most popular votes 2-class	0.85	0.87	0.75
Most popular votes 3-class	0.80	0.86	0.73
Majority vote (50%) 2-class	0.86 (for 733 statements)	0.88 (for 733 statements)	0.76 (for 720 statements)
Majority vote (50%) 3-class	0.86 (for 634 statements)	0.89 (for 696 statements)	0.76 (for 720 statements)
Majority vote (75%) 2-class	0.97 (for 452 statements)	0.96 (for 529 statements)	0.87 (for 576 statements)
Majority vote (75%) 3-class	0.97 (for 427 statements)	0.96 (for 498 statements)	0.87 (for 576 statements)
SVM 2-class Accuracy in 10-fold cross validation	0.93	0.92	0.90
SVM 3-class Accuracy in 10-fold cross validation	0.91	0.90	0.89
MLP 2-class Accuracy in 10-fold cross validation	0.92	0.91	0.90
MLP 3-class Accuracy in 10-fold cross validation	0.91	0.90	0.89
ROC AUC analysis (with $p < .05$)			
Bayesian Inference 2-class by ROC AUC	0.93	0.90	0.81
SVM 2-class ROC AUC	0.90	0.89	0.85
SVM 3-class ROC AUC	0.86	0.87	0.83
MLP 2-class ROC AUC	0.97	0.97	0.94
MLP 3-class ROC AUC	0.96	0.95	0.93

Table 2. Performance evaluation based on accuracy and ROC analysis for each of the experiments and various aggregation and evaluation measures.

Aggregation method	Experiment 1	Experiment 2	Experiment 3
Informedness			
Informedness for individual worker judgments 3-class	0.36	0.46	0.33
Informedness for most popular votes 3-class	0.41	0.49	0.08
Informedness for SVM 3-class	0.76	0.75	0.68
Informedness for MLP 3-class	0.76	0.76	0.71
Kappa-based evaluation			
Kappa for SVM 3-class	0.75	0.75	0.69
Kappa for MLP 3-class	0.78	0.77	0.71
Kappa for SVM 2-class	0.82	0.80	0.74
Kappa for MLP 2-class	0.80	0.78	0.73

Table 3. Performance evaluation based on Informedness and Kappa for each of the experiments and various aggregation and evaluation measures.

Figure 4: ROC analysis curves for each experiment.

Interestingly, as shown in Tables 2 and 3 the first and second experiment's results were consistently higher (by up to 10 accuracy points) than those of the third experiment. Therefore, we conclude that workers have quite a good ability to objectively assess the others' opinions, while their own opinions seem less reliable and consequently yield lower accuracy in classification. The 1st experiment results were always slightly higher than those of the second experiment. This finding shows that simplicity of the optional answers presented to the users is more beneficial than preciseness of the logical formulation of these answers.

The baseline individual worker judgment accuracy is quite low for both experiments (0.7 and 0.72). Approximately 30,000 individual worker judgments were produced in each of the crowdsourcing experiments. Thus, every worker in isolation does not do any better than the "all true" baseline strategy (0.73), as could be expected. However, the workers' collective decisions (after aggregation) for each statement were much more accurate. We observe that the aggregation method has a crucial influence on the results: a better aggregation method can increase the accuracy by over 45% compared to the baselines.

The statements, for which the majority vote was over 50%, can be denoted as *consensual statements*, since most of the users agree on them, and statements on which there was over 75% agreement (majority vote of over 75%) are *strongly consensual statements*. As can be observed from Table 2 the accuracy for consensual and strongly consensual statements is almost perfect (around 97% for experiment 1) and is substantially higher (but the coverage is lower) than for all the statements. The ROC analysis curves are shown in Figure 4.

Informedness and Kappa values are very similar for the different experiments and

Figure 5: Workers' vote distribution for each of the assertions for experiment 1. Axis X represents the lower bound for the number of workers who assigned the (same) given assertion type to a statement. Axis Y shows the number of statements with the number of votes higher than this bound for a specified vote. The first assertion (absolutely true: everybody would agree with this statement) is represented by blue bars, the second assertion (controversial statement) is red and the third assertion (wrong statement) is green. Recall that the maximal number of workers was 40, this is the last point on axis X showing the number of statements with exactly 40 votes for a given assertion type. For example, the left-most blue column shows that there were 500 statements with over 3 votes for the third assertion.

classification types as shown in Table 3. As could be expected they are much lower than accuracy and ROC AUC value because they show the "actual" accuracy of the classification after eliminating the influence of bias and prevalence for every class in the unbalanced data. For the MLP and SVM the Informedness is still considerably higher than for the baselines.

Figure 6: Vote distribution among the five assertions for experiment 2.

Figure 7: Vote distribution among the five assertions for experiment 3.

Figures 5-7 demonstrate the histograms of vote distribution among the different assertion types for every experiment. In particular, they display the maximal number of statements for which at least 3, 5, 10, ..., 40 of the workers agreed with a certain assertion type. As could be expected, the first assertion (“absolutely true statement”) was the most popular and consensual, so it had the highest number of statements for any number of agreeing workers for all the experiments. The last assertion (“wrong statement”) was also considerably popular with at least a few statements for the majority of thresholds on the number of agreeing workers. However, the assertions expressing the “viewpoint statements” vote were less frequent. Further analysis of the vote distribution revealed that for the third experiment (personal opinion-based) workers almost always selected radical assertions (1: “I agree with the statement since it is always true; or 5: I disagree with the statement since it is wrong”) rather than intermediate ones. For this reason, the viewpoint class got almost no correct judgments (and no votes) for this experiment. On the other hand, for the 1st and 2nd experiments there were many more votes for the intermediate answers than for the 3rd experiment. We conclude that when asked to hypothesize about experts' opinions, the workers feel less confident and more cautious and thus choose more gray-scale answers.

Consequently, this led to the extremely low value of Informedness and lower values of all the measures for the third experiment than for the first and second experiments. Accordingly, we conclude that the objective type of assertions better fits the multi-viewpoint setting of the constructed ontology.

Error analysis of the best classifiers' results reveals that the accuracy for true statements was very high (over 90%). It reaches virtually 100% accuracy with the majority vote measure. Most of the erroneous statements were also relatively easy to detect with crowdsourcing. The viewpoint statements yielded slightly lower but still quite impressive accuracy relatively to the task, around 80%. Most of the errors in their classification were when they were classed by crowds as true statements. For example, statements representing some common beliefs such as *cholesterol* causes *atherosclerosis* or *dairy product* prevents *osteoporosis* appear to be disputable in the scientific literature.

Final Remarks

Previous research proposes effective methodologies for standard consensual ontology construction, verification and evaluation. However, previous research shows that users are interested in a variety of viewpoints on the knowledge domain. This diversity cannot be expected to be achieved when individual domain experts construct the ontology due to natural leaning in favor of their personal opinions. A representative group of domain experts with diverse opinions could create a more accurate ontology. However, such a group is usually hard to be recruited. Hence, in this study we proposed and implemented a two-phase methodology for multi-viewpoint ontology construction for professional domains by non-experts. For creation of the ontological statements we propose to employ a group of information

professionals, who are skilled to locate scientific literature for a given domain and retrieve the information from it, while having no bias towards any viewpoint.

The vast majority of the statements were objectively true or viewpoint thus indicating a high quality of the produced ontology. We also show that crowdsourcing workers can accurately (with over 90% accuracy) classify statements in a multi-viewpoint ontology to distinguish between true, viewpoint and erroneous statements for a given professional domain. In addition, we found that a higher accuracy can be achieved when asking workers to assess objectively others' opinions than when they express their own opinions. Also the aggregation measure has a crucial effect on the accuracy of the results.

This research has some limitations. The employed gold standard (although double-checked) might still be imperfect and incomplete. For example, when the information specialists who construct it do not find an existing article that contradicts a given statement. The methods and results presented in this study were applied only on the single domain of diet and health. Thus, to generalize the case for a multi-viewpoint ontology construction by non-experts the methodology in future research we intend to test the approach on additional domains.

In future work we also plan to arrange an evaluation experiment with a group of domain experts with diverse opinions on the domain and compare its results to those of the non-experts. As a long-term goal we aim to develop a multi-viewpoint retrieval and diet recommendation system based on the created ontology. Further, the proposed approach can be applied on other domains of knowledge.

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